

CONDUCT OF PROVINCIAL GOVERNMENT UNDER IMPERIAL MUGHALS – A STUDY OF AKHBARAT OF PRINCE AZAM’S HEADQUARTERS IN GUJARAT 1702-04

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The Akhbarat, often translated as newsletters, are really reports of the public proceedings at the courts of the Mughal Emperor and headquarters of Provincial Governors, recorded by *wakils* or agents of nobles and high officials. Though not strictly “official”, these served as important source of information for contemporary historians, both official and unofficial.

The *akhbarat* we concern ourselves with are those sent by the *wakil* or agent of the Amber ruler, Jai Singh Sawai, to his master from Prince Azam’s headquarters at Ahmadabad.¹

Prince Azam was Governor of Gujarat from R.Y. 46 to 50 (1701 to 1705 AD).² The *Akhbarat* preserved cover only the period R.Y.s 46-47 (1702-04).

These daily reports cover a variety of subjects concerning provincial administration such as orders regarding various administrative matters (collection of tribute from Chiefdoms, administration of refractory areas, problems of law and order etc.); appointments to posts, transfers, degradations and dismissals of officials, or their reinstatement, or their leave and posting; grant of robes of honour, presentation of gifts, administration of justice; working of the branding and verification system; complaints concerning a wide range of matters (against officials, *jagirdars* etc.); information on provincial finance etc.

Many feudatory principalities were attached to the Mughal *subah* of Gujarat.³ Rajpipla was one of them, situated to the south of the Narmada river. Abul Fazl describes this principality as lying between the *sarkars* of Nadaut (of Gujarat) and Nandurbar (a *sarkar* of Malwa).⁴ The *Akhbarat*⁵ show that its chief did not pay *peshkash* regularly and willingly. The use of force ensured the collection of *peshkash*. The *Bakhshi* of the *subah*, Mir Ahmad Khan issued a *hasb-ul amr*⁶ to the *faujdar*s of the *sarkars* adjacent to the territory of Rajpipla ordering them to enforce collection *peshkash* using their armed forces. These *faujdar*s included Iltifat Khan (Godhra) Purdil Shirani (Baroda), Sayyid

Murad (Savli), Shaikh Muhammad Khan (Sankhera), Sayyid Muzaffar (Azamabad), Sayyid Muhammad Ali (posting illegible) and Mustafa Quli (Bahadurpur).⁷ Another officer named Bahadur Khan was deputed to get organised the expedition. Finally, Rs.32,000 were collected from the chief of Rajpipla as *peshkash*.

The whole process took about seven or eight months.⁸

Another important chief was the Jam (of Navanagar); his relations with Mughal authorities also appear in the *Akhbarat*.⁹ Navanagar had been conquered during the reign of Aurangzeb (in 1660 AD) and was renamed as *sarkar* Islamnagar.¹⁰ But the Jam Tamachi was probably allowed to return.¹¹ The *Akhbarat* show that Jam Lakhaji (1690-1709) was on peaceful terms with the Mughal government and sent presents and *Peshkash* in the form of horses, leopards, deer, etc.

The *akhbarat* contain references to Zamindars both submissive (revenue paying) as well as seditious (*zor talab*) in the directly governed areas of the *suba*.¹² Zamindars were considered submissive if they normally cooperated with the administration and paid their *peshkash* regularly. In return the Mughals, accommodated them in the State administrative set up. In the case of seditious (*zor talab*) zamindars, for example in Khambayat a *faujdar* of adjacent *sarkar* savli, Sayyid Murad was instructed to establish a *thana* with his armed contingent there to tackle them.

In the executive branch of provincial administration, the post of the *faujdar* ranked next to that of the *nazim* (governor). He was normally, though not invariably the head of the *sarkar*, which was both an administrative and a revenue division. In the Gujarat provincial administration, there was a *faujdar* designated as *faujdar-i gard* who policed the territory around the capital city of Ahmadabad. In the *Akhbarat* there are numerous references to this officer, his powers and functions.¹³ Amanullah Baig was appointed to this office when Prince Azam took the charge of the office of *nazim* of the province.¹⁴ Amanullah Baig was also concurrently Superintendent of Artillery (*Darogha-i Topkhana*). As *faujdar* his main function was to ensure law and order and to prevent thefts and other crimes within his jurisdiction. He was also responsible for the collection of *peshkash* from *zamindars* of the area under his charge. He is found presenting submissive *zamindars* to Prince Azam for state employment. Among his other duties was the task to get the roads (state-owned?) and houses repaired those were damaged by rains. He had control over the police or watch stations called *nakas* (toll-stations) and *Chaukis* (guard posts) within his jurisdiction. He also exacted *Rahdari* (road toll) through his subordinates, viz. *Nakakar's* and *chaukidars* from the peasants of

Petlad coming to Ahmedabad for selling grain.¹⁵ On quite a few occasions, Amanullah Baig, the *fauddar-i gard* was questioned and given instruction to control the growing conditions of insecurity in Ahmadabad.¹⁶

The *thanadar* was mainly responsible for maintenance of law and order in his area of posting and worked under the supervision of *faujdar* of the area. There are reports of disturbances in Pattan, Sorath, and Ahmedabad. In this regard, there is some interesting information about the conduct of *thanadars*.¹⁷ Two cases of absence of *thanadars* from their area of duty was reported by the *Bakhshi* Mir Ahmad Khan. In the first case, a week's time was given to them to join their duty otherwise they would be replaced. In the other case, the defaulting *thanadars* were relatives of the *Diwan* of the *suba*. But this did not prevent the governor from taking action against them. They were transferred and their *Mushrut* rank was withdrawn.

A number of instances in the form of complaints of common people against officials, *jagirdars* etc., reveal a great deal about the nature of the administration of justice and effectiveness of the provincial administration. There are also complaints of lower officials against senior officials, and of officials against fellow-officials.¹⁸

Complaints of common people are presented before governor (*Subadar*) by or through the *Darogha-i Adalat (Or Raiya)* Ghulam Muhammad. The *Nazim* also heard complaints during hunting expeditions. In the case of a complaint of common people against the *Mutassadi* of Surat, I'tibar Khan, the complainant was directed to register his grievances in the Imperial Court as the said port was under direct Imperial jurisdiction.

The complaint of an ordinary person named Lal, resident of Ahmedabad against Khalil Baig, *thanadar* of Kapadvanj, also reveals interesting information about the practical working of the *jagir* system in Gujarat. The accused had taken loan from the complainant and was not paying back. The *Bakhshi* Mir Ahmad Khan proposed that the amount be deducted from the *jagir* of the officer in question to set an example for others.

As all know, the cavalry maintained by *mansabdars* occupied the crucial position in the administrative system of the Mughal Empire. The System of Band and Review (*dagh-o-tashiha*) was introduced by Akhbar to maintain efficiency of the army. There is some evidence of strictness in the implementation of this system during the period.¹⁹ Two officers of this department in the *suba* are mentioned namely Prabhu Ram, *Mushrif* (auditor) and Khwaja Baba, *Darogha-i Dagh-*

o-Tashiha (superintendent of Branding). In the *Akhbarat*, there are repeated refernces to Sayyid Kamal Khan *faujdar* of Idar and Modasa (in *Sarkar* of Ahmedabad) in connection with *Dagh-o-tashiha* of his contingent. The non-compliance of Branding and verification by many *mansabdars* posted in Gujarat was reported by Mir Ahmad Khan, *Bakhshi* of Gujarat. Accordingly, a list of defaulters was prepared, and orders were placed to confiscate their *jagirs* to realise the state claims (*Mutaliba*) from them. Sayyid Kamal Khan was one of the *mansabdars* whose *jagir* in Rasulnagar²⁰ was resumed.

Modern historians view the shortage of *jagirs* as one of the causes for the downfall of Mughal Empire. The *Akhbarat* also furnish one instance of this.²¹ There is a petition of a *mansabdar* Safdar Khan Babi posted in Gujarat who was not allotted a *jagir*. His petition was to be forwarded to the Emperor. Another related development is reported in subsequent *Akhbarat*.²² Pargana Rasulnagar, the confiscated *jagir* of Sayyid Kamal Khan was sought by the *wakil* (agent) of Safdar Khan Babi in allotment for his client.

There were other problems for State officials as well. There is a reference to a *hasbu-l hukm*²³ prohibiting the employment of Muslims under Hindu officers.²⁴ The problems this could create are shown in subsequent *Akhbarat*.²⁵ Prince Azam refused to appoint Sayyid 'Umar and his son in the *Sarkar* to serve under Durgadas Rathor, the *faujdar* of Patan. On this Mir Ahmad Khan, *Bakhshi* pleaded that he was small and poor *mansabdar*, and large family to support, while Patan was his native place. If he was not posted under Durgadas he would be in great distress. These pleas did not, however, persuade prince Azam. On the other hand, he readily appointed Isardas to serve under Durgadas at Pattan. There are numerous reports of grant of new *mansabs*, enhancements of *mansabs*, restoration and degradations.²⁶ From these we can form an idea of power of governor (*subedar*), *Bakhshi* of *subah* and other officers in the granting of *mansabs* during this period. In some cases, the recommendations of Nawab Qudsia (wife of Prince Azam) were also accepted.

From *Akhbarat* we encounter great formalities for receiving *farmans* by the Governor of the *suba*.²⁷ The Governor, mounting on a special horse, rode out and after reaching within the *Dayra-i Farman Gah* (the encampment where the *farman* was placed) received the *farman*.

The subject of *jangal bari* (jungle clearance) by the *jagirdars* and officials is also reported in *Akhbarat*,²⁸ it was postponed due to rainy season and ploughing. The clearance had to be undertaken not for any

extension of cultivation, but for a hunting expedition of Prince Azam!²⁹

References to Leopards (*Yuzan*) by the Prince also crops up frequently in the *Akhbarat*.³⁰ The *Mirat-i Ahmadi* refers to a *Yuzkhana* (leopard establishment) with a considerable staff.

NOTES AND REFERENCES

1. *Akhbarat* of Prince Azam's headquarters in Gujarat, 46 and 47 R.Y. of Aurangzeb, bound in one volume in case 47 at the Library of the Royal Asiatic Society (Morely 133), London. Also available at Centre of Advanced Study in History, Aligarh Muslim University, Microfilm No.34, the sheets marked A1 A231.
2. Ali Muhammad Khan, *Mirat-i Ahmadi*, ed. Syed Nawab Ali, Baroda, I, 1928, pp.346-57.
3. These are listed in Ali Muhammad Khan, *Mirat-i Ahmadi*, Supplement, Baroda, 1938, pp.224-39.
4. Abul Fazl, *A'in-i Akbari*, ed. Blochmann, Calcutta, 1866-7, Vol.I, 493. Cf. *Mirat*, suppl., p.238.
5. *Akhbarat*, A3, A12, A13, A14, A23, & A86.
6. Orders issued by an officer upon instruction by a prince.
7. All places except one are shown in Atlas by Irfan Habib, *An Atlas of the Mughal Empire: Political and Economic Maps*, Dehli, 1982, Sheet 7A.
8. The expedition started in the month of Safar (R.Y. 46). completed in the Ramzan (RY 47).
9. A18, A20.
10. *Mirat-i Ahmadi*, I, p.25.
11. It was restored to Jam Tamachi in 1672 and *mansabs* were granted to him and his borther. After his death, his son Lakhaji (1690-1709) became the ruler; M.S. Commissariat, *A History of Gujarat*, Bombay, 1957, Vol.II, pp.168-9.
12. A11, A21, A39, A63, A66, A68, A75, A82, A84.
13. A1 & passim.
14. See *Mirat*, op.cit., Vol.I, p.347.
15. A77.
16. A69, A80, A84.
17. A30, A38.
18. A5, A10, A14, A18, A20, A29, A31, A41, A42, A49, A84, A85.
19. A25, A26, A34, A35, A69, A83, A89, A90.
20. In Aurangzeb's time Visalnagar situated in Patan Sarkar was renamed as Rasulnagar; *Mirat*, Suppl. 202.
21. A44 & A45.
22. A88.
23. Order issued by a minister upon the emperor's instructions.
24. A54.

25. A61 & A62.
26. A3 & passim.
27. A38.
28. A1, A2, A5, A11.
29. A49 & passim.
30. A2 & passim.